

EXPLORING SOCIAL NORMS: A PRAGMALINGUISTIC ANALYSIS OF UZBEK AND ENGLISH NOVELS

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Abstract

In order to highlight the distinctive ways social norms are represented and contested in literary discourse, this study examines the interaction of pragmatics and linguistic elements in two novels: Jane Austen's *Pride and Prejudice* (English) and Utkir Hoshimov's "The Silence" novel (Uzbek). The study emphasizes the cultural subtleties inherent in each language and the unique communication methods used by the writers through a comparative analysis of speech acts, conversational idiom, and politeness techniques. The study makes the case that pragmalinguistic analysis clarifies the complex interrelationships between language, culture, and literary meaning by analyzing these opposing viewpoints.

Keywords: English and Uzbek literature, The Silent Book, *Pride and Prejudice*, Speech Acts, Conversational Implicature, Pragmalinguistics, and Politeness Strategies

1. Introduction

Literary discourse is subject to social and cultural conventions, just like any other type of human interaction. Understanding how these norms influence communication can be gained from pragmatic linguistics, the study of language in context. This essay looks at the pragmatic elements of two books, *Pride and Prejudice* by Jane Austen and *The Silence* novel by Utkir Hoshimov, to show how the writers use language to create characters, convey meaning, and depict the social environments of their respective cultures.

2. Pragmatic Concepts in Literary Discourse:

Similar to all human interaction, discourse is influenced by social and cultural conventions. The study of language in context, or pragmatic linguistics, provides important insights into how these rules influence communication. This study looks at the pragmatic elements of two books, *Pride and Prejudice* by Jane Austen and *The Silent Book* by Utkir Hoshimov, to show how the writers use

language to create characters, transmit meaning, and depict the social environments of their various cultures.

3. Utkir Hoshimov's The Silence novel: Uzbek Cultural Variations in Conversation:

The traditional Uzbek emphasis on sensitivity and indirect communication is reflected in Hoshimov's novel, which frequently uses conversational implicature. Characters usually express their genuine emotions without saying it out loud by using proverbs, metaphors, or understatement.

- The Silence novel speech acts highlight the significance of hierarchical connections and respect in Uzbek society. Younger characters, for example, emphasize the social hierarchy and the value of civility by speaking respectfully to elders. Hoshimov's "The Silence" novel delves deeply into Uzbek society, where words are frequently overshadowed by silence. This analysis explores the pragmatic landscape of the book, looking at how the characters' language and silence reflect the complexities of Uzbek cultural values and social norms.

Hoshimov skillfully employs conversational implicature, in which shared cultural knowledge and implicit presumptions are used to imply meaning. In this situation, being silent is a potent means of expressing social meaning rather than just a lack of communication. For example, Zuhra, the main character, shows her respect for elders and her reluctance to question the status quo by remaining silent during a contentious family dispute. This quiet conveys a strong message of obedience and respect. The hierarchical structure of Uzbek society shapes the speech acts—actions carried out through language of the characters. In order to emphasize the value of deference to authority, younger characters frequently speak to elders in a courteous and respectful manner. This is clear from Zuhra's interactions with her grandmother, in which she avoids openly questioning her grandmother's beliefs and instead employs honorifics. Uzbek culture is deeply rooted in this kind of deference, and silence can serve to further entrench those power relations. Hoshimov's linguistic choices are indicative of the unique cultural background of Uzbek society. The story is interwoven with Uzbek idioms, proverbs, and metaphors that highlight the depth of Uzbek cultural traditions. These linguistic strategies frequently express intricate cultural meanings and shed light on the characters' values and worldviews. For instance, Zuhra's grandmother used the proverb "Water does not return to its source" (Suv o'z manba'siga qaytmaydi), which highlights the value of preserving the past and the irreversible nature of time. "The Silence" novel offers an engaging case study for comprehending Uzbek society's practicalities. The characters

highlight the intricacies of social dynamics and the significance of adhering to social norms through their use of language, silence, and cultural metaphors. Hoshimov's book demonstrates the nuanced ways that language and culture interact, weaving a complex web of meaning and delivering a potent message about the limitations and opportunities of communication within a particular cultural context.

4. Jane Austen's Pride and Prejudice: The Art of Humor and English Social Norms:

- **Satire and Irony:** Austen regularly employs satire and irony in her book to highlight hypocrisy and make observations about social norms. Austen's characters are able to express their genuine opinions and judgments without explicitly stating them thanks to conversational implicature, which is essential to her humorous dialogue.

- **Formal Language and Social Hierarchy:** *Pride and Prejudice*'s characters emphasize the social differences and expectations of the English gentry through formal speech acts. Etiquette and formal address are important indicators of social status.

5. Comparative Analysis: Differing Communication Methods: Both novels use pragmalinguistic elements, but their communicative styles and cultural settings are very different. Uzbek cultural norms of indirectness, deference to authority, and community-based values are all reflected in “The Silence novel”. In contrast, *Pride and Prejudice* exemplifies English social norms, emphasizing formal language, witty repartee, and a delicate dance of politeness. These divergent viewpoints demonstrate the significant impact of culture on the construction of meaning and the operation of language.

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